

The spiritual heritage of Majid Qori Qadiri

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Abstract: This article provides detailed information about the creative heritage and spiritual views of Majid Qori Qadiri. The article covers topics such as the life of the writer, his most famous works, their essence, patriotism, justice, mystical ideas. Also, the significance and relevance of Qadiri's heritage in the present period will be revealed.

Key words: Majid Qori Qadiri, Uzbek literature, mysticism, patriotism, spiritual and moral views.

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Majid Qadiri was born on October 2, 1886 (on the 4th day of Muharram, 1304 Hijri) in the Qoryogdi neighborhood of Shaikhontohur district of Tashkent city, in a religious family. His father, Abdul Kadir Khanqori, was an employee of the religious office. He studied at one of the schools in the old city of Tashkent. Then he completed his studies at the madrasa. He was fluent in Persian, Arabic, Ottoman Turkish, Russian and English.

He started his first career at the "usuli-savtiya" (old method) school in Tashkent. From 1906, he taught in Russian-style and new-style schools. Until the October coup in 1917, he taught and was the director of secondary schools in Tashkent. He was a member of the "Turon" society established at the end of 1913, a member of the "Shuroi Islamiya" (1917), "National Union" (1919) organization and worked together with national intellectuals. He was the head of the "6th Turon school" (1918-1921) established by the revolutionary movement in Tashkent. He participated in the exhibition opened in Paris in 1925 as a representative of the Uzbek SSR. On his way to Paris, he stopped in Berlin and met Uzbek students studying in Germany.

Majid Qadiri first published in Uzbek the arithmetic applied to education in new-style schools (Majid Qori, "Hisob (Basics of elementary education from mathematics)", Tashkent, 1910 (reprinted in 1913 and 1915 by the publishing house "Turkistan Kutubonus" made), geography (Majid Qori, "Jugrofiya", Tashkent 1911) and grammar books in Chigato-Turkish (Uzbek) language.

Saidrasul Azizi, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, Muhammad Rasuliy, Shokirjon Abdurahimjanov, Abdulla Avloni, Khamza Niyoz, Abdurahid Munzim, Sadridin Ainiy and others participated in publishing activities.

The successful development of the educational process in new-style schools was hindered by the lack of a single teaching methodology at that time. Proponents of introducing a new teaching method in Muslim schools have discussed this issue several times at different levels. In September 1910, Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov sent an application to the State Duma for the implementation of school education reform, asking for the introduction of general programs and textbooks at the state level in Turkestan. The same issue was discussed in May 1914 by representatives of advanced national intellectuals who gathered in the house of Shayhantohur Doha Qazi. The participants of the meeting emphasized the success of the school education process and the way to get rid of problems in the transfer of students from one school to another. At the meeting, the members of the committee responsible for the development and implementation of the unified educational methodology were confirmed, including teachers of the new method school: Munavvar Qori Abdurashidkhanov, Qori Samig Ziyoyev, Shokirjon Muhammad Rasul Abdulloh Avloni, proofreader of the newspaper "Sadoi Turkistan" and teacher of the Russian-Tuzem school. The correction worked at that time: a meeting of schools novometodnyh teachers, including the selection of a competent committee for the development of a unified curriculum Russian-system schools Abdul Majid Qari Qadiri were approved. Turkestan moderns, along with the introduction of secular sciences in educational institutions, made a great contribution to the reform of traditional sciences and learning provided invaluable assistance to low-income families who wanted it. Thanks to their efforts, the "Turon" charity fund was established in Tashkent, "Tarbiyai atfol" in Bukhara, "Gayrat" in Kokand, more than ten enterprises, publishing houses, and libraries were established. The founders of the first charitable foundation "Jamiyati Khairiya" founded in 1909 were Munavvarqari and Avloniy. On the basis of this society, in 1913, the "Turon" society was organized by the intellectuals and wealthy people of Tashkent. On the basis of this society, the "Turon" drama troupe, the "Turon" library and study hall, and the "Turkistan library" publishing house were established. Majid Qadiri was the head of the community-based "6th Turon" school from its establishment in 1918 until he transferred to Turkestan State University in 1921.

Majid Qadiri worked as the head of the "Physics Cabinet" established in 1928 at the Central Asian State University, as well as the dean of the Faculty of Arts and the head of the Department of History (1928-1930). In 1929-1930, he was criticized and falsely accused. After that, i.e. from 1930, he was a teacher at the Central Asian University in Tashkent. the basis of education) (1910) is the author of the arithmetic book, "Geography" (1911) and grammar books in the Chigato-

Turkish (Uzbek) language. Majid Qadiri was a supporter of reforms in the field of education in Turkestan and the liberation of the Uzbek people by raising the level of literacy. He published articles in the national press on the issues of education and culture, problems in the fields he worked in, and the development of Turkestan. His wife was Mehrinisokhan Mirsoatova. They had 6 children. Sons Qudduskhon, Ramzikhon, Rashodkhon, Erkinxon, Otkirkhon and daughters Nafisakhon. The name of Majid Kadirov (Majit Kadirov) was included in "Stalin's shooting lists" of the Uzbek SSR. This list includes high and mid-level leaders who worked in the field of party, national economy, military and science. The lists were compiled by the NKVD authorities after the investigation was completed and sent to the Political Bureau of the Central Committee of the CPSU(b) for approval.

With the approval of 2-5 members, it was sent to the Military Committee of the Supreme Court of the USSR for "legal formalization" with investigative work. The lists were divided into categories, category 1 (they made up the main bulk) were those sentenced to death by firing squad. The military panel of the Supreme Court (in this case - its visiting session in Tashkent) issued a verdict without the participation of the prosecutor and the lawyer in the so-called special order of the court.

A maximum of 20-30 minutes was allocated for consideration of the case, without the possibility of appeal against the decision, and it was carried out with the execution of the sentence within hours. The list including Majid Qadiri was approved by Stalin, Molotov and Zhdanov on September 12, 1938.

The first prosecution against Majid Qadiri began in 1929. At the beginning of 1929, he was deprived of the membership of the Communist Party due to unproven suspicions. In 1930, he was dismissed from all responsible positions. The reason was the slanders organized by the supporters of the proletariat and the Soviet government in 1929-1930 and the feuilletons printed in the press.

Summary

Majid Qori Qadiri's creative heritage and spiritual views are an integral part of Uzbek literature and culture. His works and opinions serve the spiritual and moral perfection of our people and remain relevant even today. The study and promotion of Qadiri's work is of great importance in the formation of national pride.

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